

Draft status

As on 23-01-2020, the following data entry protocol is recommended in order to record 'Ref' and 'Src' in the metadata table.

Reference, 'Ref' field:

1. Link (URL) where the reference source could be retrieved;
E.g. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-y0494e.pdf>

Source, 'Src' field:

1. Source is the reference's citation, which is following the APA referencing format (recommended).
2. Format used to record 'Src' is depending on the source type. Below are some examples of the format;

Book - Authored work:

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Year). *Title of work: Subtitle* (edition.). (Volume(s)). Publisher.
E.g.: Colclough, B., & Colclough, J. (1999). *A challenge to change*. London, England: Thorsons.

Book - Edited work:

Editor, A. A. (Ed.). (Year). *Title of work: Subtitle* (edition.). (Volume(s)). Publisher.
Snyder, C. R. (Ed.). (1999). *Coping: The psychology of what works*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

Book Chapters:

Author of Part, A. A. (Year). Title of chapter or part. In A. A. Editor & B. B. Editor (Eds.), *Title: Subtitle of book* (edition., inclusive page numbers). Publisher.
E.g.: Hine, C. (2001). Ethnography in the laboratory. In D. N. Gellner & E. Hirsch (Eds.), *Inside organizations: Anthropologists at work* (pp. 61-76). Oxford, England: Berg.

Electronic Book:

Author A. A. (Year). Title of work. Retrieved from URL.
E.g.: De Huff, E. W. (2000.). *Taytay's tales: Traditional Pueblo Indian tales*. Retrieved from <https://digital.library.upenn.edu/women/dehuff/taytay/taytay.html>

Journal Article - Authored work:

Article Author, A. A., & Article Author, B. B. (Year). Title of article. Title of Journal, volume number(issue number), inclusive page numbers.

E.g.:

Hanna, K. (2007). Adsorption of aromatic carboxylate compounds on the surface of synthesized iron oxide-coated sands. *Applied Geochemistry*, 22(9), 2045-2053.

Parker, G., & Roy, K. (2001). Adolescent depression: A review. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 35(5), 572-580.

Journal Article - No author:

Title of article. (Year, Date). Title of Journal, volume number(issue number), inclusive page numbers.

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E.g.: The pain of being a caffeine freak. (2001, October 6). *New Scientist*, 172(2311), 27.

Theses - Unpublished:

Author, A. A. (Year). *Title of thesis: Subtitle* [Unpublished thesis type]. Name of University.

E.g.: Hos, J. (2005). *Mechanochemically synthesized nanomaterials for intermediate temperature solid oxide fuel cell membranes* [Unpublished PhD thesis]. University of Western Australia.

Published Theses:

Author, A. A. (Year). *Title of thesis: Subtitle*. Publisher.

E.g.: May, B. (2007). *A survey of radial velocities in the zodiacal dust cloud*. Canopus Publishing.

Repository:

Author, A. A. (Year). *Title of thesis: Subtitle (Identifier, if applicable)* [Thesis type, Name of University].

Repository Name. URL

E.g.: Ryan, J. (2014). *The measurement and meaning of coping in psychiatric patients* [PhD thesis, Murdoch University]. Murdoch University Research Repository.

<https://researchrepository.murdoch.edu.au/id/eprint/24254/>

Internet Documents/Webpage or Piece of Online Content

Author, A. A. (Year). *Title: Subtitle* (Edition). Publisher. Retrieved from (URL).

If the page's author is not listed, start with the title instead. If the date of publication is not listed, use the abbreviation (n.d.).

E.g.: Spotlight Resources. (n.d.). Retrieved from

https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/about_the_owl/owl_information/spotlight_resources.html

Newspaper article from the internet

Article Author, A. A. (Year, date). Title of article. *Title of Newspaper*. Retrieved from (URL).

E.g.: Hilts, P. J. (1999, February 16). In forecasting their emotions, most people flunk out. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com>

3. In addition, Zotero or Mendeley tools are recommended to be used for generating the citations.

References:

Murdoch University.(2020). APA - Referencing Guide. Retrieved from

<https://libguides.murdoch.edu.au/APA/entries>

Purdue University. (2020). Apa Formatting and Style Guide. Retrieved from

https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/research_and_citation/apa_style/apa_formatting_and_style_guide/general_format.html